

INTRODUCTION

The fishery complex is an important part of the Russian Federation's economy, especially for coastal regions. It provides jobs, contributes to the development of local communities and generates income.

Due to changing consumer preferences, the demand for fish and seafood is increasing. This creates the need for sustainable fisheries development to meet the needs of the population.

Relevant interest in the introduction of new technologies and techniques in fish farming and fisheries can improve the efficiency and sustainability of the industry. This includes aquaculture, biotechnology and digitalization of processes.

Thus, the fishery complex development in Russia is an urgent topic that requires a comprehensive approach and attention from the state, business and scientific community.

Literature Review

The fishery complex of Russia is a complex sector of the economy, its raw material base being industrial fishing and fish farming. It includes various types of activities, ranging from forecasting the raw material base of the industry to organizing domestic and foreign trade in fish products. In maintaining food security of the Russian Federation, preserving aquatic bioresources and improving the quality of life of the population, the fishery complex occupies an important place.

The main types of fishery activities include fishing (harvesting), fish farming (fish breeding), as well as processing and production of the main types of fish products.

The problem of illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing activities in the world is one of the most serious threats to the sustainable management of fishery resources. Illegal fishing depletes fish stocks and disrupts ecosystems. Numerous regions of the world lack effective fisheries control mechanisms.

R. Hilborn and D. Ovando write that the continued overexploitation of fisheries worldwide is evidence that current fisheries management approaches are failing and that more precautionary management approaches are needed. The authors insist that managed stocks are improving while unmanaged stocks are not [1].

The 27 existing species of sturgeon and paddlefish (order Acipenseriformes) represent a unique and relict fish lineage. Sturgeon black caviar is one of the most valuable wildlife commodities on earth. E. K. Pikitch et al. point out that sturgeon and paddlefish are threatened worldwide, their long-term survival in the wild at risk. The authors write that it is necessary to improve domestic and international fisheries management and pay attention to habitat and species restoration [2].

Overexploitation of both natural and enhanced sturgeon stocks for caviar production, along with severe habitat degradation, led to dramatic declines in natural populations. The authors discuss future trends in large-scale caviar production, taking into account some of the scenarios that the industry is likely to face, including market uncertainty (reduced profitability, product diversification) and opportunities (reduced pressure on natural stocks, improved image) [3].

According to N. A. Miller, transshipment at sea, unloading of catch from a fishing vessel onto a refrigerated vessel far from a port can conceal the actual source of the catch, complicating sustainable fisheries management and may allow illegally caught fish to enter the legitimate seafood market. Transshipment often occurs in regions of unclear jurisdiction, where politicians or law enforcement may be slow to respond to a problem they cannot see. Transshipment behavior on the high seas is relatively common, with vessels responsible for 40% of the high seas fishery having had at least one encounter with a transshipment vessel during this time period [4].

S. Sakamoto et al. write that now is the time for conservation measures for Arctic fish species which are indispensable for ecosystem structure and function and may be subject to unprecedented catches. Management and coordination methods by Arctic coastal states are needed to mitigate the impacts of industrial fisheries in Arctic Ocean [5].

The problem of unreported and unregulated fishing activities is relevant for Russia and a key challenge the sustainable management of fishery resources faces.

Thus, according to J. Wilhelmsen & K. L. Gjerde, the Barents Sea contains some of the most valuable fish resources in the world, including the world's largest cod stocks. Since the mid-1970s, Norway and the Soviet Union/Russia jointly managed the most important stocks in the region through the Joint Russian-Norwegian Fisheries Commission. The authors present the main precautionary measures adopted by the Commission, including catch control regulations [6].

G. Hønneland presents the results of interviews with a number of Norwegian and Russian fishermen who comment on compliance with fishing regulations in the Barents Sea. The authors note a high level of compliance in this region. Fishermen note respectful attitude on the part of inspectors [7].

Sh. C. Clarke et al. provide an estimate of the amount of sockeye salmon caught in eastern Russia, based on trade data from Japan, China and Korea, in the context of potentially large-scale IUU fishing activity. The authors compare their data with official Russian catch figures to estimate the 'excess' catch resulting from IUU fishing operations. The results support the hypothesis that there is a significant amount of excess catch of Russian sockeye salmon entering East Asian markets. The actual catch exceeds the registered level by 60-90% [8].

G. Pramod wrote that illegal and unregistered catches accounted for 20-32% of all seafood imported into the United States in 2011. The authors present studies of supply

chains of tuna, wild shrimp and Russian pollock, salmon and crab imported to the United States processed by China [9].

Thus, the scientific problem of sustainable management of fish resources in Russia is the need to develop and implement effective methods and strategies that will ensure a balance between economic interests, environmental sustainability and social needs.

Effective management of fish resources requires accurate and up-to-date data on the state of fish populations, their biology, ecology and the influence of external factors.

Scientific research must take into account changes in climate and propose adaptive management strategies. The need to control catches and prevent overfishing requires developing science-based quotas and monitoring methods. Sustainable management must consider not only fisheries but also the effects of other factors such as pollution of water bodies, habitat destruction, and competition with invasive species. Sustainable management must take into account the interests of local communities that depend on fisheries resources for their livelihoods. This requires an integrated approach that includes participation of local people in decision making. Given that numerous fishery resources are transboundary in nature, international cooperation and harmonization with other countries is necessary to ensure sustainable use of the resources.

The article aims: to analyze measures for sustainable management of fishery resources in Russia in the context of illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials of the study were the periodicals data on fishery complex development trends in various countries, including Russia: ICES Journal of Marine Science, Fish and Fisheries, Journal of Applied Ichthyology, Marine Policy and others.

Materials of statistical reporting of the RF (including data of the Federal State Statistics Service on production, consumption and export of fish and seafood), its subjects and the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia for the last decades were also considered. The research used abstract-logical, monographic, calculative-constructive, comparative analysis and statistical methods.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Global economic trends require introducing a new model of economic development capable of ensuring dynamic and sustainable growth of the Russian economy, based on the

internal factors of state competitiveness, and above all on improving the economic efficiency of production [10]. Currently, it is required that the national economy develops at an accelerated pace (above the world average), relying on the main goal of economic growth, which is social well-being and high standards of living of Russian citizens, quality infrastructure development and food security of the country.

The solution of the outlined tasks requires a systematic and comprehensive approach that allows solving the current problems of ensuring socio-economic stability and, at the same time, carrying out structural reorganization of the Russian economy [11].

In this regard, an additional long-term planning document is required for the fishery complex, which is the 'Strategy for the development of the fishery complex of the RF up to 2030'. This Strategy envisages the achievement of the following strategic objectives until 2030 [12]:

1) ensuring national food security, which will be achieved in ensuring the average per capita consumption of fish and fish products in the amount of 22-27 kg/person per year and achieving a self-sufficiency indicator of 80-90%;

2) developing human potential expressed in the number of new highly qualified jobs created (25 thousand by 2030) and in the growth of labor productivity up to 150%;

3) increasing the aggregate contribution to GDP with an average annual growth of 5% and growth of gross profit of enterprises per ton of catch of 150%;

4) strengthening leadership in the world markets (share in the European market of pollock and cod (haddock) products 25% and share in the Asian-Pacific market of pollock and salmon products 10%);

5) developing and implementing a national system of ecological certification of fisheries and production facilities;

6) considering and consolidating (at the federal level) legislative acts regarding the realization of catches and pricing, economic connection between the extractive fleet (fishing companies) and the economy of the country, preservation and increase of workplaces in the industry, etc.);

7) establishing order and sharply increasing jobs in the industry, etc.;

8) bringing order and dramatically increasing efficiency in managing federally owned port infrastructure facilities;

9) reducing the negative impact on the environment, the indicator of which should be the FAO award by 2025.

Notably, in 2020-2021, the industry developed dynamically. Russian users continued to exercise the right to harvest (catch) aquatic biological resources (ABR) in accordance with the Government of the RF Resolution No. 643 of August 25, 2008 'On the preparation and conclusion of an agreement for the use of aquatic biological resources, the total allowable catch of which is not established'. In 2021, the recommended allowable catch for industrial fishing

in the internal waters of the RF, territorial sea, exclusive economic zone on the continental shelf of the RF, Azov and Caspian seas, as well as in the areas of international treaties of the RF in the field of fishing and conservation of aquatic bioresources for all fishery basins of the fishing industry amounted to 1961.9 thousand tons, which is 85.0 thousand tons or 4.5% more than the recommended allowable catch. The following species of aquatic biological resources were harvested (caught) in 2021 in the fishery basins of Russia [13]:

- 1) in the Far Eastern fishery basin: flounders, Pacific herring, rays, gobies, saffron cod, Japanese pilchard, mackerel;
- 2) in the Northern Fishery Basin: wolffish, flounder, saffron cod, laminaria, northern prawn;
- 3) in the Azov-Black Sea fishery basin: khamsa, sprat, gobies, so-iuy mullet;
- 4) in the Volga-Caspian fishery basin: bream, pike, carp, tench, freshwater catfish, Brazhnikov's shad, sprat, river herring;
- 5) in the Western fishery basin: pikeperch, perch, burbot, European smelt, vendace, bream.

In 2021, the utilization of the recommended catch volumes of aquaculture resources amounted to 535.85 thousand tons or 27.31% of the total recommended catch (1,961.9 thousand tons). The total catch of Japanese pilchard, mackerel and saury in Russia as of December 31, 2021, was 344.0 thousand tons, which is 53.7 thousand tons or 15.6% less than in 2020. The main share of the catch is Japanese pilchard – 255.9 thousand tons, which is 59.6 thousand tons less than the 2020 level, and the catch of mackerel was 87.5 thousand tons, which is 6.1 thousand tons higher than the 2020 level.

According to a preliminary estimate, FSSS for 2021 productions of fish, processed and canned, amounted to 4360.3 thousand tons, and the planned value, according to the State Program RRC is 4407.1 thousand tons. 100 percent fulfillment of the planned value was expected after FSSS published actual data in the 3rd quarter of 2022. The indicator of inland waters area coverage of the RF by measures of state control (supervision) to detect and suppress violations of the legislation in the field of fishing and conservation of aquatic biological resources at the end of 2021 was at the level of the planned value, 45% [14].

The dynamics of aquatic biological resources release into water bodies of fishery importance within the approved state task (to the base period) in 2021 amounted to 44.01% (the planned value was 124.1%). This indicator is due to the fact that the activities performed by the institutions subordinated to Federal Agency for Fishery at spawning and rearing farms, in accordance with paragraph 2 of the Rules for the organization of artificial reproduction of aquatic biological resources, approved by the Government of the RF of February 12, 2014, No. 99 'On Approval of the Rules for the organization of artificial reproduction of aquatic biological resources', are not works on artificial reproduction of aquatic biological resources. In this regard, the state task was amended to reduce the number of aquatic biological resources

(except for sturgeon) released into water bodies of fishery significance, which amounted to 2,110.28 million pieces [Ibid].

Thus, the institutions subordinated to Federal Agency for Fishery carried out releases of aquatic biological resources in the amount of 2,712.6 million pieces, which is 26.6% higher than the planned value. The volume of commercial aquaculture production (including planting material) in 2021 amounted to 356.6 thousand tons, which is 28 thousand tons (or 8.5%) higher than in 2020.

In the sustainable development of the fishery complex, an important role belongs to research activities aimed to comprehensively study aquatic bioresources in order to organize their rational sustainable use. In 2021, the federal budget funds allocated under the subprogram 'Science and Innovations' of the State Program of the Fishery Complex were used to carry out 649 expeditions to collect materials on the biology and state of stocks of fishery objects in the exclusive economic zones of the RF, on the continental shelf and in the territorial sea, and in the internal waters. The actual value of the subprogram indicator 'Volume of the estimated potential of the raw material base of aquatic biological resources (annual value)' was 5410 thousand tons, which corresponds to the planned value of the indicator of the State Program RRC [Ibid].

According to Federal State Statistics Service, in 2021, the export volume of fish, fish products and seafood amounted to 2,044.2 thousand tons. In monetary terms (in current export prices) it is 5,953.1 million USD (or 114.5% of the plan), which is 11.7% higher than in 2020. The volume of imports of fish, fish products and seafood in 2021 compared to 2020 increased by 24.1 thousand tons (or 4%) and amounted to 623.1 thousand tons. In monetary terms, imports in 2021 amounted to 2308.5 million USD, which is 242 million USD (or 11.7%) more than in 2020.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In recent years, the fishery complex of Russia demonstrates a steady growth due to the support of the state. Both the volume of fresh or chilled fish production and its export to the CIS and non-CIS countries increased. It can be stated with confidence that fish production is developing, new production technologies are appearing and old ones are being improved, and energy efficiency of production facilities is increasing. Reduction of energy intensity of finished products, as well as development of new culinary production technologies will contribute to the growth of average per capita consumption of fish and fish products by the population. All these trends in the industry have a positive impact on food security and

sustainable socio-economic development of the RF; providing these in the long term is of paramount importance.

The prospects for the fishery complex development in Russia are quite promising, given the country's vast water resources and the growing demand for fish and seafood both in the domestic and foreign markets.

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